
Educational Activities for Prevention of Child Marriage and Consanguineous Marriage for Students of Ethnic Semi-Boarding Junior High Schools, Dien Bien District, Dien Bien Province, Vietnam

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Abstract

There were over many participants who were village elders, village heads, family heads, clan heads, parents; people of marriageable age; juvenile; students at Ethnic Minority Boarding Schools, high schools and junior high schools. However, the situation of violations of child marriage in Dien Bien district, Dien Bien province is still complicated, especially the situation occurs with junior high school students who are ethnic minorities. Facing the above situation, ethnic minority schools – which are specialized schools, established for children of ethnic minorities, children of ethnic minority families who permanently settle in areas with special socio-economic condition difficulties in order to contribute to the training of cadres in these regions. The junior high school is organized and operates according to the regulations of the charter of the junior high school – a level of education in the education system in Vietnam, located between primary school and high school; lower secondary school lasts 4 years from 6th to 9th grade, the age of children from 11 to 15 should pay special attention to education on prevention of early marriage and consanguineous marriage for students. Stemming from those reasons, the author chose the research topic. The

paper finds out that education for these children is a very necessary task we must take it into consideration.

Keywords: children, child marriage, consanguineous marriage education

1. INTRODUCTION

Dien Bien province, Vietnam is a mountainous and border province with 10 district-level administrative units (including 4 border districts and 5 districts under the Government's project 30a); 129 communes, wards and townships (including 29 border communes, 110 communes with special difficulties); 1,788 villages, hamlets, residential quarters; There are 19 ethnic groups living with nearly 550,000 people, of which over 80% are ethnic minorities, living in areas with difficult terrain, difficult transportation, and uneven population distribution [1].

In recent years, in Dien Bien province, there has been a situation of students being from ethnic minorities getting into early marriage (Premature marriage is a marriage between a man and a woman when one or both parties do not meet the legal requirements for marriage. The age of marriage in accordance with the law of Vietnam. Men get married when they are under 20 years old and women get married when they are less than 18 years old) and consanguineous marriage (marriage or cohabitation as husband and wife between a man and a woman in the same close relative within three generations). According to the report of Dien Bien Provincial People's Committee on the preliminary review of 5 years of implementation "Project to reduce child marriage and consanguineous marriage in ethnic minority areas of Dien Bien province in 2015 - 2020" shows that, in the period of 2015 – 2019, the province had 18,948 married couples. Of which, there are 4,965 child marriage couples, accounting for 26.2%; 26 consanguineous marriages, accounting for 0.13%. This number mainly occurs in the area of the Hmong ethnic group. In order to raise awareness about child marriage and consanguineous marriage as well as reduce early marriage and consanguineous marriage, from 2015 to 2019, Dien Bien province has implemented many activities in propaganda and advocacy to raise public awareness. From 2016 to now, Dien Bien province has held more than 60 propaganda conferences on the Law on Marriage and Family in 64 communes; established 59 propaganda clubs in 59 communes of 7 districts and towns in the province.

2. OBJECTS OF INVESTIGATION AND RESEARCH METHODS

To survey the current status of educational activities to prevent early marriage and consanguineous marriage for students in ethnic minority semi-boarding high schools in Dien Bien district, Dien Bien province, 106 staff and 214 students from 03 schools, Nua Ngam Commune Ethnic Minority Semi-boarding Junior High School, Muong Nha Commune Ethnic

Minority Semi-boarding Junior High School, Phu Luong Ethic Minority Semi-boarding Junior High School in Dien Bien District, Dien Bien Province participated in the survey [2].

A combination of research methods was used: questionnaire survey method, observation method, in-depth interview method and activity product research method.

When using the survey method by questionnaire, the scoring convention is shown as follows: Each item has options and is conventionalized by different score levels including 1 point equal infrequent, weak results /least; 2 points equal average; 3 points equal done regularly, the results are at a good level.

Rating (according to the score range):

+ Level 1: $1,00 \leq \text{Average score} \leq 1,66$: Irregularity; Weak/poor results.

+ Level 2: $1,67 < \text{Average score} \leq 2,33$: Medium level ; Average result.

+ Level 3: $2,34 < \text{Average score} \leq 3,00$: Usually; Good results

3. CURRENT STATUS OF EDUCATIONAL ACTIVITIES TO PREVENT EARLY MARRIAGE AND CONSANGUINEOUS MARRIAGE FOR STUDENTS

To survey the current status of educational activities to prevent early marriage and consanguineous marriage for students in secondary schools in Dien Bien district, Dien Bien province, we focus on the following contents: research on the current situation. educational content, educational methods, educational engagement forces and educational outcomes [3].

3.1 The current situation of educational content to prevent child marriage and consanguineous marriage for students in ethnic minority semi-boarding secondary schools in Dien Bien district, Dien Bien province

In order to find out the current status of educational content to prevent child marriage and consanguineous marriage for students in junior high schools for ethnic minorities in Dien Bien district, Dien Bien province, Vietnam, we used the survey method by questionnaire combined with the in-depth interview method to survey the opinions of teachers and students, the results in the table are shown in Table 1.

Table1. Level of implementation and results of implementation of educational activities on prevention of child marriage and consanguineous marriage for students in junior high schools for ethnic minorities in Dien Bien district, Dien Bien province.

Content	Administrative staffs, Teachers (n= 106)		Students (n= 214)		Total (n= 320)	
	Implementa tion level	Implementa tion	Implementa tion level	Implementa tion	Implementa tion level	Implementa tion

	efficiency		efficiency		efficiency		efficiency		efficiency		efficiency	
	\bar{X}	Level										
Knowledge of law on marriage and family	2.39	2	1.69	4	1.39	10	1.67	7	1.72	10	1.68	7
Knowledge about adolescent sex and reproductive health	1.84	6	1.86	2	2.03	4	1.70	6	1.97	3	1.75	3
Knowledge about child marriage: System of legal documents, concepts, manifestations, causes, harms, ways to prevent child marriage, consanguineous marriage	2.12	3	1.67	5	2.13	2	2.27	2	2.13	2	2.07	2
Knowledge about consanguineous marriage: System of legal documents, concepts, manifestations, causes, harms, ways to prevent child marriage, consanguineous marriage	1.52	10	1.67	5	2.07	3	1.57	9	1.88	5	1.61	9
Adolescent reproductive health care skills	1.82	7	1.75	3	1.90	6	1.71	5	1.88	6	1.73	4
Self-control skills,	1.75	9	1.60	9	1.82	9	1.75	3	1.79	9	1.70	5

rejection skills, etc.												
Skills to convince parents to prevent child marriage and consanguineous marriage	1.75	8	1.64	7	1.82	7	1.46	10	1.80	8	1.52	10
Skills to seek help	1.89	4	1.57	10	1.82	7	1.74	4	1.84	7	1.68	6
Struggle to condemn outdated customs and practices that infringe on children's rights and human rights to marriage and race maintenance	1.85	5	1.63	8	2.00	5	1.63	8	1.95	4	1.63	8
Actively and proactively abide by the school's rules and regulations, building a friendly school, a happy school, and mutual friends helping each other.	2.73	1	1.96	1	2.18	1	2.29	1	2.36	1	2.18	1
Encourage friends and relatives to abide by the law on marriage and family	1.49	11	1.45	11	1.28	10	1.39	11	1.35	11	1.41	11

Through the above data table, it can be seen that, in the secondary schools of Ethnic Minority Junior High Schools, various contents are being implemented to educate the prevention of child marriage and consanguineous marriage for students [3]. Among the mentioned contents, the most frequently implemented groups of content are: Educating the sense of proactive compliance with school rules and regulations, building a friendly school, a happy school, and friends, mutual affection and mutual help [4]; Knowledge of gender, adolescent reproductive health and knowledge of child marriage with a system of legal documents, concepts, manifestations, causes, harms, ways to prevent child

marriage and consanguineous system. Through observation, we found that from the beginning of the school year, all schools have developed detailed and complete rules and regulations and required students to strictly follow them. The table of rules and regulations in the school is a guideline to guide the behavior, attitude and behavior of students in the school environment based on the regulations of the Ministry of Education and Training. Every student is required to follow the set rules and regulations when going to school. In addition to the general regulations for all students, the Ethnic Minority Junior High Schools also have specific rules for day-boarding students on behavior, accommodation, hygiene... Through interviews with teachers DBH-Teacher, in charge of administration of the Nua Ngam Commune Secondary School, said: "The rules and regulations for semi-boarding students are of great significance because it not simply regulates the behavior and attitudes of students in and out of school. Besides classroom hours, the rules of semi-boarding also regulate social relationships, friendship relationships, and emotional relationships in daily life when students stay at the school. As a result, students adhere to the time of activities and study in a scientific and reasonable manner [5]. Students train themselves with good habits, form and develop important skills in behavior and communication. continue, know how to build and maintain good emotional relationships, pure friendship among students".

Another content that schools are interested in related to carrying out educational activities to prevent child marriage and consanguineous marriage is education in the sense of law observance; Law on Marriage and Family [4]. The survey shows that this content is implemented in many different forms, integrated into the core subjects, basic educational activities such as civic education, experiential activities, educational activities outside of class time, class activities, flag salutation at the beginning of the week, group activities, dormitories... However, the organization of legal education topics and topics for students monotonous and unattractive, the organizers lacked in-depth knowledge of the law, so they could not attract students to participate [6].

The group of contents that are implemented infrequently and with the lowest results are: Education on knowledge of consanguineous marriage: Legal system, concepts, manifestations, causes, harms ways to prevent child marriage (ranked 9th); mobilizing friends and relatives to abide by the law on marriage and family (ranked 10th); Skills in persuading parents to prevent child marriage, consanguineous marriage (ranked 11th)... The causes of this situation are explained by school teachers as follows: Legal document system, concepts, and expressions, causes, harms, and ways to prevent child marriage have not been fully provided to schools. Teachers' tasks are still many, so they do not have the conditions to learn and explore, then they have not been focused on continuing and in-depth education; The work of propagating, disseminating and educating the parents of students, and mobilizing relatives and friends on the prevention of child marriage and consanguineous marriage is still facing many difficulties due to many factors such as: language barriers language because many people do not know how to speak general Vietnamese, low education level, many people are illiterate, propaganda objects do not participate in propaganda sessions. Influenced by customs and outdated conceptions in

marriage, outdated customs still exist as deeply ingrained in each people. There are backward customs such as forcing a wife, where parents place their children to sit. Parents' care and concern for their children in many families is still loose, superficial... Leads to a situation where children may become pregnant unexpectedly, thereby leading to marriage before the legal age. This is also a limitation in education on prevention of child marriage and consanguineous marriage for junior high school students [7].

3.2 Current status of educational methods to prevent child marriage and consanguineous marriage for students in ethnic minorities junior high in Dien Bien district, Dien Bien province

To find out the current status of educational methods to prevent child marriage and consanguineous marriage for students in ethnic minority junior high schools for ethnic minorities in Dien Bien district, Dien Bien province, Vietnam, we used the survey method by questionnaire combined with the in-depth interview method to survey the opinions of teachers and students, the results in the table are shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Current status of educational methods to prevent child marriage and consanguineous marriage for students in junior high schools for ethnic minorities in Dien Bien district, Dien Bien province

Content	Administrative staffs, Teachers (n= 106)				Students (n= 214)				Total (n= 320)			
	Implementation level		Implementation efficiency		Implementation level		Implementation efficiency		Implementation level		Implementation efficiency	
	\bar{X}	Level	\bar{X}	Level	\bar{X}	Level	\bar{X}	Level	\bar{X}	Level	\bar{X}	Level
Brainstorming method	2.67	1	2.46	1	2.40	1	2.22	1	2.49	1	2.30	1
Group discussion method	2.09	5	2.23	6	1.92	6	2.00	4	1.98	5	2.07	4
Chat method	2.43	2	2.42	2	2.34	2	2.20	2	2.37	2	2.28	2
Role-playing method	2.39	3	2.24	5	1.98	4	2.00	4	2.11	4	2.08	3
Problem solving method	2.35	4	2.08	8	2.21	3	2.02	3	2.25	3	2.04	6
Methods of creating educational	1.9	6	2.27	4	1.97	5	1.96	7	1.95	6	2.07	5

situations												
Methods of creating public opinion	1.89	7	2.31	3	1.89	7	1.73	9	1.89	7	1.93	9
Reward method	1.65	9	1.88	9	1.72	9	1.97	6	1.70	9	1.94	8
Punishment method	1.83	8	2.18	7	1.88	8	1.86	8	1.87	8	1.97	7

Looking at the above data table, we can see that teachers of Ethnic Minority Junior High Schools in Dien Bien district, Dien Bien province have used a variety of educational methods to prevent child marriage and consanguineous marriage for the students. However, the level and results of using different and different educational methods, in which: The methods regularly used by teachers to educate students on prevention of child marriage and consanguineous marriage are: Ethnic minority people in the Ethnic Minority Junior High Schools are: brainstorming method, role-playing method, problem solving method. These are the methods frequently used in teaching activities, in organizing educational activities and in other activities. To explain this problem, we interviewed a teacher of LTH from Nua Ngam Commune Ethnic Minority School. She said, "To use brainstorming, role-playing, and problem-solving methods, we put students in front of difficult situations. In situations that force them to think, they are allowed to role-play the characters in the main stories so that they can remember the educational content more accurately and longer [8]. For against child marriage, consanguineous marriage, they are often associated with the law, so we found that it is difficult for students to remember by mere theory, so we designed questions or raised situations and let them put reasons and give answers. With such methods, we see that they remember for a long time and understand correctly. Consequently, these methods are preferred to use."

Among the above methods, there are some methods that teachers rarely use and are not very effective: the method of reward and punishment. To explain this, the teacher said that: "The majority of ethnic minority students are honest and very friendly, but their critical thinking has not yet developed, so students are still afraid to give their personal views on a certain phenomenon. Because of the fear of being set an example or being reprimanded, these methods have not been widely applied."

In terms of effectiveness, the role-playing method, the brainstorming method, and the conversation method were the most effective. To explain this, we interviewed the VTN, a teacher at Phu Luong Commune Ethnic Minority Secondary School. She said, "In the process of participating in learning when students are role-playing, they are reinforced both in theory and practical skills when using theoretical knowledge to handle situations and events that they role-play, so the efficiency is very high; when conducting conversations with students, teachers have conducted convey and integrate theoretical content of law and law related to the content of

education on prevention of child marriage and consanguineous marriage into issues in life in a gentle way, so students also absorb well; the problem of preventing child marriage and consanguineous marriage brought up by teachers has put students in problematic situations that force them to brainstorm, think, and then come up with solutions to solve the problem". Therefore, both teachers and students highly appreciate these three methods [9].

The method that according to teachers is not effective is the method of group discussion, problem solving, reward and punishment. According to the teacher's explanation, during the group discussion, the children will be arranged with many objects with different genders and levels. The characteristics of ethnic minority children are very shy, timid, not brave, but the issue of child marriage and consanguineous marriage are sensitive. Therefore, in the process of exchanging and discussing, they are very shy and do not dare to express personal views. Therefore, the goal of education to prevent child marriage and consanguineous marriage has not achieved the expected results. In addition, for the method of reward and punishment, although it also has the advantage of encouraging or timely adjusting to the students' attitudes and sense of learning, the main goal of educational activities is propaganda and prevention. As a result, the method of punishment is not focused by the teachers.

According to the teacher's opinion, there is a method that teachers rarely use, but the effectiveness is highly appreciated, which is to create public opinion. This is also the result of the boarding school environment. Because the students study together, live together, and participate in extra-curricular activities, they are very conscious of building public opinion. Bad and inappropriate behaviors are condemned; good behavior and good example are praised by the students, so students know how to use public opinion to develop their capacity. This is an opinion we are very interested in to propose recommendations to improve the quality of education to prevent child marriage and consanguineous marriage for students [10].

3.3 The current situation of subjects implementing education on prevention of child marriage and consanguineous marriage for students in junior high schools for ethnic minorities in Dien Bien district, Dien Bien province

To find out the actual situation of subjects implementing education on prevention of child marriage and consanguineous marriage for students in junior high schools for ethnic minorities in Dien Bien district, Dien Bien province, Vietnam, we used the survey method by questionnaire combined with the in-depth interview method to survey the opinions of teachers and students. The results in the table are shown in Table 3.

Table3. The actual situation of subjects implementing education on prevention of child marriage and consanguineous marriage for students in junior high schools for ethnic minorities in Dien Bien district, Dien Bien province

Content	Administrative staffs, Teachers (n= 106)		Students (n= 214)		Total (n= 320)	
	Implementa	Implementa tion	Implementa	Implementa tion	Implementa	Implemen tation

	tion level		efficiency		tion level		efficiency		tion level		efficiency	
	\bar{X}	Level										
Psychological counselors	1.25	11	1.52	8	1.79	6	1.60	7	1.61	7	1.58	7
Staffs in charge of semi-boarding students	1.63	6	1.59	4	2.26	2	2.18	2	2.05	3	1.99	2
Homeroom teacher	1.50	9	1.58	5	2.50	1	2.43	1	2.17	1	2.15	1
Subject teacher	1.54	7	1.61	2	2.23	4	1.89	5	2.00	4	1.80	5
Teacher in charge of Union-Team	1.67	5	1.58	5	2.25	3	2.15	3	2.06	2	1.96	3
School board	1.70	4	1.58	5	1.66	7	1.67	6	1.68	6	1.64	6
Education Department Specialist	1.90	3	1.61	2	1.33	10	1.37	8	1.52	9	1.45	8
Student Parents Association	1.91	2	1.49	9	1.30	11	1.32	10	1.50	10	1.38	10
Family	1.99	1	1.46	11	1.36	9	1.30	11	1.57	8	1.35	11
Local government officials	1.52	8	1.49	9	1.38	8	1.33	9	1.43	11	1.38	9
School medical staff	1.50	9	1.89	1	2.15	5	1.90	4	1.93	5	1.89	4

Table 3.3 shows that educational activities to prevent child marriage and consanguineous marriage in Ethnic Minority Junior High Schools are carried out by many different subjects. The group of subjects participating in the most frequent and effective implementation of education on prevention of child marriage and consanguineous marriage for students in ethnic minority semi-boarding secondary schools are homeroom teachers; staffs and concurrent teachers in charge of managing semi-boarding students; teacher in charge of Union - Team. Through practical observations, we find that the homeroom teacher is the person who has the greatest influence on the educational process of students [2]. The homeroom teacher is the person who regularly interacts with the students, is the person closest and cares most often with the students, so the

assignment of the responsibility to the homeroom teacher in the prevention of child marriage and close marriage is important. Besides the attention of the homeroom teacher, there are also concurrent teachers in charge of managing semi-boarding students. This force is diverse, including the Board of Directors, administrative teachers, subject teachers, medical staff, security guards, support staff, etc., who are assigned specific tasks with responsibilities for organizing and managing all activities from food, accommodation, activities, entertainment, health care... for students staying at the school. They are responsible people who are trusted by the school board, parents' association, and local government leaders. This force is gradually becoming the effective arm of the school in the care and education of students in general and the prevention of child marriage and consanguineous marriage for part-boarding students at ethnic minority middle school in particular. Many teachers and staff of the semi-boarding student management team have done their job well, being a reliable address for students to share their thoughts, feelings, and get helps when they have difficulties. In addition to the above two subjects, the teacher in charge of the Union - Team is also very close to all students in the school. As the person who directly conducts education topics on prevention of child marriage and consanguineous marriage, this is also a highly appreciated object.

The group of subjects that have the lowest influence on the quality of education on prevention of child marriage and consanguineous marriage are: Local government officials; Student Parents Association; Family. According to Article 9 of the 2016 Law on Children, "Agencies, organizations, educational institutions, families and individuals have the responsibility to ensure the exercise of children's rights and obligations; to support and create conditions for children exercise their rights and obligations as prescribed by law; coordinate and exchange information in the process of implementation". Thus, in addition to schools, local organizations and unions are responsible for the exercise of children's rights and obligations, including: Vietnam Fatherland Front and members of the Front (Communist Youth Union; Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam Women's Union, Associations related to child protection; etc.); Families and individuals in society are responsible for the exercise of children's rights and obligations. However, in reality when organizing educational activities for students at schools, the role of the mentioned subjects has not been effective. This is the basis for us to propose recommendations to improve the quality of education to prevent child marriage and consanguineous marriage for students.

3.4 Current status of education results on prevention of child marriage and consanguineous marriage for students of ethnic minority semi-boarding high schools in Dien Bien district, Dien Bien province

We have observed in reality from the school year 2018 - 2019, 2019 - 2020 in the three schools, there were still some situations of child marriage, which is shown in the following table:

Table4. Statistics on the number of students from Ethnic Minority High Schools and Secondary Schools getting married early in the school year 2018-2019, 2019 - 2020

No.	Dien Bien District Ethic Minority Junior High School	Academic year	Total number of students	Number of students of child marriage	
				No.	%
1	Nua Ngam Commune Ethic Minority Semi-Boarding Junior High School	2018 - 2019	419	1	0,2
		2019 - 2020	403	1	0,2
2	Phu Luong Commune Ethic Minority Semi-Boarding Junior High School	2018 - 2019	382	1	0,3
		2019 - 2020	378	1	0,3
3	Muong Nha Commune Ethic Minority Semi-Boarding Junior High School	2018 - 2019	690	1	0,1
		2019 - 2020	687	2	0,3

The above results show that in the two school years 2018-2019 and 2019-2020, there were 1 to 2 students. In which, Muong Nha ethnic minority school has 3 cases (0.2%); Nua Ngam ethnic minority school has 2 students (0.2%); Phu Luong ethnic minority school has 2 students (0.3%). That means that every year in Dien Bien district, Dien Bien province, child marriage still occurs. However, with the encouragement and advice of the teachers, the children continued to study until the end of secondary school after getting married. This is a picture of child marriage in Dien Bien district in particular and Dien Bien province in the current period [5].

There are many causes that directly or indirectly affect the situation of child marriage and consanguineous marriage of students in the school environment such as: influences from family customs, local forces forcing children to get married, get married early; due to difficult family economic conditions, poverty, students have to drop out of school to get married or get married to have more people to work; due to the provisions of the law, the sanctions are not strong enough to prevent and deter cases of child marriage and consanguineous marriage; due to the people's intellectual level, awareness about the consequences of child marriage and consanguineous marriage is still limited; The propaganda and advocacy work for families and students about child marriage and consanguineous marriage is conducted irregularly and ineffectively. Each factor has certain impacts on the management and organization of educational activities to prevent child marriage and consanguineous marriage for students of the principal [7]. Therefore, the management subject needs to find appropriate measures to manage and organize education to prevent child marriage and consanguineous marriage in lower

secondary schools in an effective and practical way, thus contributing to the regresschild marriage and consanguineous marriage in Vietnam today.

4. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Ethnic minority semi-boarding secondary schools in Dien Bien district, Dien Bien province have paid attention to the implementation of educational activities to prevent child marriage and consanguineous marriage for students and have achieved certain results. However, in reality, there are still cases of students getting into child marriage and consanguineous marriage.

In order to improve the quality of education to effectively prevent child marriage and consanguineous marriage for students, we propose the following recommendations: The school conducts extra-curricular activities more often in terms of experience activities, action programs for students, teachers, students' parents... with educational content on prevention of child marriage and consanguineous marriage in the school environment for the purpose of raising awareness of students individuals in preventing and minimizing the situation of child marriage of students; Teachers need to actively develop a plan to integrate education on prevention of child marriage and consanguineous marriage into the cultural teaching program to provide more knowledge, training and awareness education for students; Homeroom teachers need to pay closer attention to students, for example, if they see students showing unusual expressions in the male-female emotional relationship, they need to find out the matter clearly, and at the same time coordinate with their families to keep up the right time to help and orient them; In particular, it is necessary to strengthen the coordination of schools, families and society in education to prevent child marriage and consanguineous marriage for students.

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